

From individual to joint species distribution models: a comparison of model complexity and predictive performance

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Importance of Explanatory Variables by Taxon in the Individual Models

The following plots compare the calibrated probabilities of occurrence and the explanatory variables for all taxa in the individual species distribution models. The calibrated probabilities of occurrence (based on maximum likelihood estimates of the taxon-specific parameters) produce strong positive or negative responses for explanatory variables with a good explanatory power (with the exception of the individual models overfitting for rare taxa). Taxa are ordered by decreasing number of occurrences and show a variety of distinct response curves for the selected explanatory variables.

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Chironomidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Limoniidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Simuliidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Oligochaeta

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_alpinus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Empididae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_rhodani*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Ceratopogonidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Psychodidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Elmidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Isoperla

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Planariidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_muticus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Gammaridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Athericidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Prostigmata

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_tristis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Hydraenidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_lateralis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_mortoni*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Nematoda

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Sericostoma*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Scirtidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Habroleptoides_confusa*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Blephariceridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_helveticus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Brachyptera_risi*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Sphaeriidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dixidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Amphinemura*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Odontocerum_albicorne*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Dictyogenus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Tinodes

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Tipulidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Plectrocnemia

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_minima*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_discolor*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_loyolaea*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Epeorus_alpicola*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_braueri*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Epeorus_assimilis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Stratiomyidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Philopotamus_ludificatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Habrophlebia_lauta*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dugesiidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Centroptilum_luteolum*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_venosus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_puthzi*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Chloroperla_susemicheli*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Paraleptophlebia_submarginata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_picteti*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_lutheri*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dytiscidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Thaumaleidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_hirticornis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_alpestris*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Capnioneura_nemuroides*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_brevistyla*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ephemera_danica*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_picteti*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Habroleptoides_auberti*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Metanoea*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Siphonoperla_torrentium*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Glossosoma*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_nigra*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Lymnaeidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_siltalai*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Electrogena_ujhelyii*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Rhabdiopteryx

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Perloides

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Erpobdellidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_intricata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Perla_grandis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Wormaldia*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Asellidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Cryptothrix_nebulicola*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_nimborum*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Sialidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Ptychopteridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Hydrophilidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_alpinus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Glossiphoniidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_annulatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Cordulegastridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Siphonoperla_montana*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ephemerebella_mucronata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Serratella ignita*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_hybrida*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_nivata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Anthomyiidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Leuctra_major

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Lype

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Hydroptilidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_biguttatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecdyonurus_torrentis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_degrangei*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Perla_marginata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemurella_pictetii*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Ancyclus

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Tabanidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Polycentropus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Potamophylax_cingulatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_melanchaetes*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_semicolorata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_dorieri*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Hydrobiidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Goeridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Gyrinidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Calopterygidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dinocras

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Lepidostomatidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Brachyptera_seticornis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_gratianopolitana*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_grischuna*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecclisopteryx madida*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Rhagionidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Physidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_praemorsa*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Melampophylax_mucoreus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_venus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Niphargidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Chloroperla_tripunctata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_marginata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Agapetus

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Torleya_major*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_nigrescens*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_intermedia*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_flexuosa*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_muelleri*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_tenuis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Electrogena_lateralis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Capnia*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Haliplidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dolichopodidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Micrasema_morosum*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Psychomyia_pusilla*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_macrura*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_instabilis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Syrphidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Siphonurus_lacustris*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_stigmatica*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_praecox*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Corixidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Planorbidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_schmidi*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis vardarensis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_bucерatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Scathophagidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_pubescens*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Allogamus_auricollis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_torrentium*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Mystacides*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Coenagrionidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dryopidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Synagapetus_dubitans*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_rosinae*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Catagapetus_nigrans*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Astacidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Osmyliidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Piscicolidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Dendrocoelidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_melanonyx*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Glyptotaelius_pellucidus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Psephenidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Gerridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_meyeri*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_landai*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Philopotamus_variegatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Synagapetus iridipennis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Halesus_radiatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_fasciata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus monticola*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Lepidoptera

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Veliidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_alpinus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Ernodes

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Platycnemididae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Cnidaria

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Athripsodes

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_rivulorum*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Anabolia

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_inermis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_allobrogica*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ptilocolepus_granulatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Cloeon_dipterum*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Baetis_nexus

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_horaria*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_dinarica*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_nimborella*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Bithyniidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Valvatidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Aphelocheiridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Chaetopteryx_major*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ecclisopteryx_guttulata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_niger*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_cambrica*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Mesoveliidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Holocentropus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Besdolus_imhoffi*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Protonemura_auberti*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_simulatrix*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_saxonica*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_dorsalis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Diplectrona atra*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Chaoboridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Conosporhlyax_consorts*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Habrophlebia_eldae*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Limnephilus_lunatus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Notidobia_ciliaris*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_liebenauae*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Gomphidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Baetis_nubecularis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Oecetis_testacea*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Caenis_luctuosa*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Hymenoptera

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Beraea_pullata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Micrasema_setiferum*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Cheumatopsyche_lepida*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ceraclea_annulicornis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Nemoura_cinerea*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_mixtus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Agrypnia

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Habrophlebia_fusca*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Hydropsyche_pellucidula*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Sciomyzidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Ephyridae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Halesus_rubricollis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_rauscheri*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Beraea_maurus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Curculionidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Notonectidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_glareosa*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_pseudosignifera*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Potamanthus_luteus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Heptagenia_sulphurea*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Micropterna_nycterobia*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Ceraclea_dissimilis*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Chrysomelidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhithrogena_carpatoalpina*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Leuctra_armata*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Culicidae

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Drusus_chrysotus*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for *Rhyacophila_rectispina*

Probability of occurrence vs explanatory variables for Acroloxiidae

